

SELF-CONSISTENT PROPERTIES OF THE MWCN AND HEXAGONAL ARRAYS AS COMPOSITE REINFORCEMENTS

Pascal Hubert

McGill University

Montréal, Québec, H3A 2K6, Canada

R. Byron Pipes

The University of Akron, Polymer Engineering Academic Center

Akron, OH 44325-0301, USA

SUMMARY: The discovery of single walled carbon nanotubes has the potential to lead the next revolution in the development of high performance materials. Carbon nanotubes are hexagonal arrangement of carbon atoms, a graphene sheet, which has been rolled to form a tube. They are synthesized by various techniques, including arc discharge, chemical vapor deposition and laser ablation. The single wall carbon nanotube (SWCN) consists of a single layer of graphene and has a diameter of 0.6-1.8 nm and a length of 500-1000 nm. The SWCN has extraordinary properties, Young's modulus of 1000 GPa, strain to failure of 15-30%, thermal conductivity of 3000 W/m²K which would make them the ideal reinforcement. On the other hand multi walled carbon nanotubes (MWCN) have larger diameters. They consist of multi layers of graphene sheets that have been rolled into a series of concentric layers to form a multi wall tube. It is of great interest to develop consistent property relationship for MWCN's and their arrays as they are used in more applications compared to SWCN.

In this work, a self-consistent set of relationships is developed for the physical properties of multi walled carbon nanotubes and their hexagonal arrays as a function of the chiral vector integer pair, (n,m) . Properties include effective radius, density, principal Young's modulus and specific Young's modulus. Relationships between weight fraction and volume fraction of MWCN and their arrays are developed for the full range of polymeric mixtures. Examples are presented for various values of polymer density and for multiple MWCN diameters. Comparisons of the predicted properties to those reported in the literature are discussed and issues relating to the use of MWCN as reinforcements in polymeric composites are articulated.

KEYWORDS: multi-walled carbon nanotubes, density, modulus, hexagonal array, volume fraction, weight fraction

INTRODUCTION

The use of carbon nanotubes for reinforcement of polymeric materials has been given as one of the primary applications for this new material form since its discovery more than a decade ago [1]. Yet the debate continues as to how the extraordinary properties of these nanoscale material forms will translate to the macroscale. Indeed, when properties are quoted for the single-walled (SWCN) and multi-walled

(MWCN) carbon nanotubes (see Figure 1), no single reference volume has emerged as the standard upon which to measure volume dependent properties. For example, when the density of the SWCN is given, often the representative volume used in the calculation is the entire cylindrical volume enclosed by the carbon atom crystal lattice. Yet when the effective Young's modulus is reported, it is often done so only for the volume of the monoatomic layer of carbon atoms and estimates of 1 TPa are often reported. The

Figure 1 TEM Image of single-walled and multi-walled carbon nanotubes [2].

need for a self-consistent set of properties is evident. In the present work, the issues of nanoscale material properties of the multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWCN) are discussed in the context of heterogeneous materials wherein the carbon nanotube (CNT) is suspended in a second continuous phase, either individually or as hexagonal arrays. While no structural material is continuous at the nanoscale, it is important to establish uniform ways of describing the interaction between the CNT and a second, suspending material.

The present work is a continuation of an earlier paper by the authors [3] wherein the properties of the SWCN and its hexagonal arrays are developed and the relationship between weight fraction and volume fraction for SWCN in polymer mixtures were developed. The current paper focuses on the physical properties of the MWCN and its hexagonal array. Since the MWCN are often combined with polymers to form nanocomposites, relationships between weight fraction and volume fraction of MWCN and their arrays are developed for the full range of polymeric mixtures.

CARBON NANOTUBE GEOMETRY

The basic element of the carbon nanotube is a single graphene sheet rolled into a cylindrical geometry. SWCN differ from MWCN only in that MWCN are made up of multiple and collinear cylindrical layers of graphene separated by the van der Waals distance, while SWCN consist of a single cylindrical graphene layer. Since MWCN are essentially multiple layers of graphene, they can be considered as nested SWCN. The SWCN has been described as a single graphene sheet rolled up with varying degrees of twist as described by its chiral vector, C_h [4]:

$$C_h = na_1 + ma_2 \quad (1)$$

where a_1 and a_2 are unit vectors in the two-dimensional hexagonal lattice and “ n ” and “ m ” are integers. As an example, the armchair nanotube corresponds to the condition where $m = n$ and the chiral angle is 30 degrees, while for the zig-zag configuration, either m or $n = 0$ and the chiral angle is zero. The SWCN radius is given in the following relation as a function of the integer pair and the C-C bond length, b [4]:

$$R_n = \frac{b}{2\pi} \sqrt{3} \Lambda \quad (10^{-9} m) \quad (2)$$

where

$$\Lambda = \sqrt{(n^2 + m^2 + mn)} \quad (3)$$

For the SWCN, the C-C bond length is equal to 0.142 nm [4]. The diameter of the SWCN (n,m) can vary over a wide range, e.g. 0.68 nm for (5,5) and 7.52 nm for (0,96). The remaining geometric descriptors of the SWCN are the wall thickness and length. Several investigators have taken the SWCN wall thickness to be equal to that of the separation distance of graphene sheets of 0.07-0.34 nanometers [4]. The length of the SWCN will likely be a function of both carbon nanotube process technologies, handling and mixing of the SWCN with the polymeric phase, just as it is for discontinuous fiber systems. However, a recent study has revealed a distribution of lengths with a mean length of 480 nanometers [5]. Other authors [6,7] have measured bundle lengths of up to 20,000 nm.

The geometry of the MWCN is illustrated in Figure 2 where the external radius R_{me} is defined in terms of the effective internal radius, R_{mo} , the number of layers, N and the van der Waals equilibrium distance, μ .

$$R_{me} = R_{mo} + N\mu \quad (10^{-9} m) \quad (4)$$

Here the van der Waals distance is defined as the equilibrium separation between layers and is taken to be constant throughout the MWCN as illustrated in Figure 2. The internal radius, R_{mo} is clearly shown as the radius of the innermost graphene layer, minus one-half the van der Waals distance. Each layer may be described by a unique values of the integer pair (n,m) and the chiral vector need not be the same for all layers. MWCN are defined by the chirality of the inner tube and the number of layers, (n,m)_N (e.g. (5,5)₁₀). The radius of the innermost graphene layer can be obtained from the radius of a SWCN with a given chirality:

$$R_{mo} = R_n(n, m) - \frac{\mu}{2} = \frac{b}{2\pi} \sqrt{3}\Lambda - \frac{\mu}{2} \quad (10^{-9} m) \quad (5)$$

For MWCN, the intershell spacing, μ , was found to vary from 0.34-0.39 nm [8]. Using a value of 0.34 nm, Table 1 presents dimensions of typical MWCN found in the literature. MWCN produced by a carbon arc discharge process have an outer diameter ranging from 2-20 nm and an inner diameter ranging from 1-3 nm [9].

Table 1 Dimensions of MWCN.

Tube definition (n,m) _N	Number of layers	Inside diameter (nm)	Outside diameter (nm)
(5,5) ₂	2	0.68	1.36
(5,5) ₁₀	10	0.68	6.78
(10,10) ₁₄	14	1.36	10.2
(15,15) ₁₆	16	2.0	12.2
(30,30) ₂₈	28	4.0	22.0

The synthesis of carbon nanotubes typically results in the generation of collimated arrays of nanotubes with hexagonal cross-sectional arrangement [7]. The MWCN array is replaced by the effective reinforcement array shown in Figure 3. For a constant separation distance between the nanotubes equal to the intershell spacing μ , the MWCN volume fraction of the hexagonal array, V_a , is a constant and is equal to a volume packing fraction of 0.906:

$$V_a = \frac{\pi}{2\sqrt{3}} = 0.906 \quad (6)$$

Figure 2 MWCN geometry.

Figure 3 MWCN array geometry.

DENSITY

The density of the MWCN may be defined by the mass of the carbon atoms contained within the representative volume. Here the definition of volume is critical to the outcome of the prediction. In this work, it is taken to be equal to the volume within a cylinder of radius R_{me} . The density of the MWCN in the present work is defined by the number of carbon atoms contained in a representative volume element multiplied by the molecular weight of the carbon atom and divided by the volume of the a cylinder of diameter equal to twice the effective radius of the nanotube as given in equation (4). First, it is necessary to express the number of carbon atoms per unit length, N_i for one layer of the multi-walled nanotube:

$$N_i = \frac{4\Lambda_i}{3b} \quad (\text{Carbon atoms / nm}) \quad (7)$$

where Λ_i is based on the chirality for the i^{th} shell defining the MWCN. The density of the MWCN is determined by summing the number of carbon atoms for all layers and dividing by the volume containing the atoms:

$$\rho_m = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N N_i k}{\pi R_{me}^2} \quad (\text{g / cm}^3) \quad (8)$$

where $k = 0.01995$ to yield ρ_m in units of g/cm^3 . The constant k was obtained from the relation for the atomic mass of the carbon atom:

$$k = (1.660539 \times 10^{-24} \text{ g})(12.011)(1 \times 10^{21} \text{ nm}^3 / \text{cm}^3) = 0.01995 \text{ g} \cdot \text{nm}^3 / \text{cm}^3 \quad (9)$$

MWCN density as a function of diameter is presented in Figure 4. These results show that the MWCN density increase with an increase in outer diameter. Here the inside diameter of the MWCN is fixed by the choice of the innermost SWCN layer and the diameter is increased by adding layers to achieve the increased diameter. Note that the MWCN density converges to a value of 2.2 g/cm^3 , the density of single crystal graphite [7].

The density of the hexagonal array of MWCN is the product of the MWCN density in an array configuration (equation 8) and the volume packing fraction of the hexagonal array (equation 6):

$$\rho_{ma} = V_a \rho_m = \frac{\pi}{2\sqrt{3}} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N N_i k}{\pi R_{me}^2} \quad (\text{g / cm}^3) \quad (10)$$

Like the density of the individual MWCN, the array density shows a significant increase with MWCN diameter (Figure 4). It is noteworthy that density of the MWCN array differs from that of the MWCN only by the product of the maximum volume fraction (0.906).

Figure 4 MWCN and MWCN array density.

YOUNG'S MODULUS

In the following development the authors assume that the MWCN is made of continuous multi-layers of graphene with a separation distance μ . The MWCN Young's modulus is based on the stiffness of a graphene sheet. Several authors have confused the discussion by reducing their data or making their calculations so that the Young's modulus of the atomic layer is determined rather than the effective modulus of the MWCN based on the volume occupied. In the following, the authors utilize the volume element to calculate Young's modulus wherein the volume is consistent with that utilized in the calculation of density. The Young's modulus of the MWCN can be expressed as the sum of the contributions of each of its layers:

$$E_m = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N G\mu \left[(R_{ni} + \mu/2)^2 - (R_{ni} - \mu/2)^2 \right]}{R_{me}^2} \quad (GPa) \quad (11)$$

where G is the stiffness of a graphene sheet. The value of G used in this paper is 349.8 GPa·nm which corresponds to a modulus of 1029 GPa for a graphene sheet with a thickness of 0.34 nm. The increase in Young's modulus with diameter for the MWCN, shown in Figure 5, mirrors its increase in density with increase in diameter (see Figure 4). It is noteworthy that the asymptotic value of Young's modulus of the MWCN exceeds that for high strength carbon fiber by more than a factor of 3.0 [10]. Utilizing the Young's modulus, E_m , of individual MWCN in an array configuration, we obtain the following MWCN array modulus:

$$E_{ma} = V_a E_m = \frac{\pi}{2\sqrt{3}} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N G\mu \left[(R_{ni} + \mu/2)^2 - (R_{ni} - \mu/2)^2 \right]}{R_{me}^2} \quad (GPa) \quad (12)$$

Results for the principal modulus of the MWCN array are shown in Figure 5. Comparison of MWCN modulus predicted by equation 11 and published data is presented in Figure 6. The results show that equation 11 captures the change in Young's modulus for small diameters for a (5,5)_N MWCN also predicted in reference [11] using a strain energy approach. At larger diameters, the results from bending experiments on single MWCN using an AFM probe compare well with our predictions for a (15,15)_N MWCN.

Figure 5 MWCN and MWCN array modulus.

Figure 6 MWCN modulus compared to published data.

WEIGHT FRACTION VERSUS VOLUME FRACTION

With the establishment of the density of the MWCN, it is now possible to develop a relationship between weight fraction and volume fraction of MWCN in a mixture with a second material such as a polymer. Consider a MWCN/polymer mixture of density, ρ_c with a MWCN volume fraction, V_m , a MWCN density of ρ_m and a polymer density of ρ_p . The MWCN volume fraction can be expressed as follows:

$$V_m = \frac{\rho_c - \rho_p}{\rho_m - \rho_p} \quad (13)$$

It is also possible to express the MWCN volume fraction in terms of its weight fraction, W_m :

$$V_m = \frac{\rho_c}{\rho_m} W_m = \frac{W_m \rho_p}{W_m \rho_p + (1 - W_m) \rho_m} \quad (14)$$

Similarly, the relationship for the volume fraction of MWCN arrays, V_a , in terms of the corresponding weight fraction, W_a , for MWCN arrays of density ρ_{ma} in a polymer mixture is:

$$V_a = \frac{\rho_c}{\rho_m} W_a = \frac{W_a \rho_p}{W_a \rho_p + (1 - W_a) \rho_{ma}} \quad (15)$$

Using equations (8) for ρ_m and (10) for ρ_{ma} we can obtain the MWCN and MWCN array volume fraction

using equations (14) and (15) respectively.

The relationship between volume fraction and weight fraction for MWCN-polymer mixtures is shown in Figure 7 for $(30,30)_N$ MWCN with 5, 10 and 20 layers ($N=5, 10$ and 20) mixed with a polymer having a density of 1 g/cm^3 . These results show that as the number of layers defining the MWCN increases, the non-linearity in the relationship increases. This is because the difference between the MWCN and polymer densities increases as the number of layers defining the MWCN increases. The influence of variations in polymer density upon the relationship between volume and weight fraction is shown in Figure 8 for a $(30,30)_{10}$ MWCN. Here increasing the polymer density decreases the non-linearity in the relationship. This is because as the polymer density increases from 0.8 to 1.2 g/cm^3 , it approaches the density of the MWCN which is 1.97 g/cm^3 . Again, as the density difference between the polymer and MWCN decreases, the non-linearity in the weight fraction volume fraction is also decreasing. These relationships, based on a consistent definition of volume and thereby, volume fraction, are necessary for micromechanics calculations to determine the effective properties of nanotube reinforced polymers.

Figure 7 MWCN volume fraction versus weight fraction (polymer density = 1 g/cm^3).

CONCLUSION

Relationships have been developed for the geometric and physical properties of MWCN that require only the specification of chiral vector defining the innermost shell and the van der Waals distances defining the interlayer distance. A common volume element provides for density and modulus property predictions that are consistent. Results presented for the MWCN show that both density and principal Young's modulus increase with increase in MWCN diameter. The utility of the density relationships developed earlier are exploited for the determination of the relationship between weight and volume fraction in MWCN in mixtures.

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